

ORGANIZATIONAL RESILIENCE DURING THE CORONAVIRUS PANDEMIC: THE INFLUENCE OF CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY STRATEGY AND MODERATING ROLE OF ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP AND INNOVATIVE BEHAVIOUR

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This Study is derived from Pooneh EMAMVERDI's Master Thesis Study "Organizational Resilience During The Coronavirus Pandemic: The Influence Of Corporate Social Responsibility Strategy and Moderating Role Of Organizational Citizenship And Innovative Behaviour

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Abstract: Organizational Resilience” has been defined also as organizational resistance capabilities in literatures which facilitate the flexibility and conformity of the organization with stressful conditions to be able to preserve his competitive conditions or to utilize the occurred undesired possible conditions in his favor. The present study is a descriptive survey research. Research population is personnel of Parsian Azadi chain hotels in Iran. Available sampling was used to choose the sample group in which 210 subjects were gathered and analyzed at last. A questionnaire with confirmed validity and reliability was used as the study variable measuring tool. Conformity factor analysis was used for data deductive analysis and structural equations model was particularly used to test the hypothesis. The study results revealed that CSR toward employee had a significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior and innovative behavior. CSR toward customers had a significant effect on innovative behavior and organizational citizenship behavior had a significant impact on innovative behavior. In fact, innovative behavior could improve organizational resilience indicators since this variable affects integrity, agility and robustness.

Keywords: Organizational Resilience, innovative behavior, Corporate social responsibility, Organizational citizenship behavior.

1. INTRODUCTION

Organizational resilience is defined in the research literature as a series of organizational resilience capabilities that enable an organization to cope with stressful situations, maintain its competitive position, and even take advantage of potential adverse conditions (Kantur and Iseri-Say, 2015). Organizational resilience can be developed and managed through “a set of specific organizational capabilities, routines, practices and processes by which a firm conceptually orients itself, acts to

move forward, and creates a setting of diversity and adjustable integration” (Bouaziz and Smaoui, 2018). Although it has not been long since the onset of Covid-19 disease, numerous studies (Goodell, 2020; Rizwan et al. 2020) have been conducted on the impact of this pandemic on global businesses. At the time when the spread of the disease has still been in its infancy, Goodell (2020) predicted in an article entitled “COVID-19 and finance: Agendas for future research” that in the near future, the financial world will see a major impact of the disease on financial affair.

Simionescu and Dumitrescu (2016) in their research have deeply linked CRS and organizational resilience. Moreover, in the business world, activities related to corporate social responsibility have caused companies to experience significant growth and development in terms of both goods and services in the long run (Aguinis & Glavas, 2012; Zhang et al 2020). Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has become a tool through which companies can not only help maintain and improve company’s competitive advantage and credibility, but also motivate employees about Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB).

Mafabi et al. (2012) report that organizations that have survived in business have been those that have consciously sought to redesign their businesses. In Iran, the tourism industry, like hotels has experienced great financial losses due to the Corona pandemic. Many tourism companies and hotels have had to reduce their staff which has caused a high cost to both staff and the organization. The ability of a system to absorb disturbances and having a fundamental function in maintaining its structure is defined as Organizational resilience (Walker and Salt, 2006). The practical purpose of this study is to design a path through modeling for tourism industry through which they can have greater flexibility when encountering crisis. The present study will also contribute to the current body of knowledge in organizational resilience. This study will first examine the role of CRS in the tourism industry and will evaluate its role in creating organizational citizenship, improving desire and innovative behavior, and finally creating organizational resilience. In fact, the main purpose of this research is the influence of Corporate Social Responsibility Strategy on Organizational resilience.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Organizational Resilience

Today, organizations are being challenged increasingly. Economic meltdown, world financial crisis, uncertainty in competence market and social political and pandemic diseases threaten competition and survive of an organization.

To overcome these circumstances successfully, organizations have to create strength potential. Organizational resilience includes ability to deal with stressful circumstances, ability to retain positions and ability to handle unfavorable utilization conditions (Kantur and Iseri-Say, 2015).

Organizational resilience was firstly emerged in Ecology and environment by Holling (1973). Holling (1973), who defined ecosystem resilience as an indication to measure its capability to absorb variations. Organizational resilience is defined as a wider concept than compatibility is, as it means that an organization empowers when encounters with stressful events and conditions (Cooper et.al 2014)

Resilience encompasses an organization capability to create dynamic models and commercial strategies varying the concurrent conditions before the needs intensively emerge (Cooper et.al, 2014).

So, resilience is not limited to the organization ability to adsorb shocks or creating resistance and strength when disorderliness happens. Resilience converts undesired conditions into advantages when facing with such terms. (Kantur and Iseri-Say 2015).

2.2 Corporate Social Responsibility

Numerous definitions have been presented for CSR, however, a unified definition has not yet been represented (Kunda et al., 2018). Research has been started about this matter mainly discussing on businessmen responsibilities (Bowen, 1953) which has been led to empirical studies about its impacts on financial and profitability of an organization, and resulted in alternative concepts emerging, as well as social performance of the organization, the company civilization performance and commercial ethics.

2.3 The Role of Social Responsibility on Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Employees’ perception of their organization social accountability plays a vital role in forming their OCB in organization (Jones, 2010). Lee and Kim (2013) reported the positive role of CSR on OCB in hoteling. So, CSR can be considered as a sustainable force to advocate the environment (Glavas and Piderit, 2009) in order lead the hotel staff to OCB for the hotel

environment and the bigger community. Furthermore, the stronger people seek the organization benefits beyond their personal benefits, i.e. humanism values and self-transcendental, the more they appear their green traits (Steg and Vlek, 2009). Therefore, CSR which nurtures altruistic environmental values, (Jin et al, 2013) can catalyze OCB among the employees (Prasad and Mukherjee, 2014), and might create a good support for pre-environmental initiations.

2.4 Corporate Social Responsibility and Innovative Behavior

Innovative behavior is a procedure for innovation and creativity within which employees utilize their knowledge and capabilities well. This can be considered as the staff actions using their personal experiences for developing valuable perspectives and creating novel products and services (Wu and Shi, 2007). According to the social interaction theory, staff will participate innovative services actively only when they believe the company attempts are as intensive as they try to apply their innovations.

CRE regularly decreases the staff stress and improves job satisfaction, happiness and self-esteem (Wingerden et.al, 2018). As a result, the staff recognizes themselves as a part of the company and improves their commitment toward the company or organization (Wei et.al, 2014). Ultimately, CRE encourages the staff to do extra actions like innovation in services.

2.5 The Role of Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Organizational Innovation Behavior

Several researchers have figured out that OCB is correlated with innovation (Sharma & Bhatnagar, 2014; Xerri & Brunetto, 2013). Podsakoff et al (2000) found that OCB influences the organizational effectiveness which supports innovation.

Sharma and Bhatnagar (2014), after a wide range of literature review, suggested a model in which OCB predicted an innovative behavior in employees. Brunetto and Xerri (2013) also reported that OCB is in a significant relation with innovative behavior. Those who want to help others or show OCB do not expect to receive advantages against it. This type of humanism attempts to increase the others' well-being (Fang & Chiu, 2010). It is expected that employees experiencing positive relations at their work place show a reactive response to their colleagues such as their managers. Researches on assessment of employee's behavior for OCB is significant and innovative behaviors mostly necessitate the employees to do over their duties.

2.6 The Role of Innovative Behavior in Improving Organizational Resilience

Organizations survived in industry, continuously do their knowledge attempts to adjust and renovate procedure design and commercial structures such as main qualifications. These organizations develop potentials through learning and training to make knowledge for complying with the business environment which leads to organization resilience. Based on organizational capabilities, organizational resilience is designed through converting the commercial approaches to methods which are in accordance with environmental needs under which they act (Chaharbaghi et al., 2005). O'Regan and Ghobadian (2011) have asserted the need for a revolution through innovation, where a senior executive director has reported that continuous innovation is significant for the organization surviving (Garcia-Morales et al., 2006).

For better services, some organizations adapt with their customers request for hierarchical structure classification, work process re-design, sometimes key repairs carried out by individuals (Ongaro, 2004). This needs innovation through which organizations can define and perform new managers, structures, processes and qualifications.

Organizations seeking for renovating their structures and processes, try to recognize pressure factors for variation like reducing the risks, high operative costs, quality and quantity, adjusting acts and etc. (Pritchard and Armistead, 1999). From this point of view, Christensen (1997) suggests disordering innovation as a revolution strategy for renovating the trade procedures. According to Christensen's (1997) "disordering innovation" concept, successful firms do their innovations recognizing and responding customers' needs considering reactions to the competitors' strategies. Christensen and Rayno (2003) also asserted that managers can make strategic decisions about leading and invest on disordered growth, on what kind of product they produce, which customers should be considered, which processes should be developed, how to avoid merchandizing, how to force an organization for disordered growth, how to innovate. Nevertheless, other authors have concluded that resilient should have the ability to design novel commercial processes which are evaluated for efficiency and effectiveness. (Deselnicu et al 2007)

Findings also suggested that there is a significant relation between organizational innovation and organizational resilience (Mafabi et al, 2012). Hamel and Valikangas (2003) also asserted that organizational resilience needs innovation.

3. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

As mentioned, the main purpose of this research is The Influence of Corporate Social Responsibility Strategy and Moderating Role of Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Innovative Behavior. Figure 2.1 exhibits the hypothesized model of this study. Two dimensions of corporate social responsibility variables (CSR toward employee and CSR toward customer). Whereas, Organizational citizenship behavior and Innovative Behavior are represented as the mediators and Organizational resilience as the dependent variable. Therefore, stated below are the proposed hypotheses:

- H1. CSR toward employee positively affects organizational citizenship behavior
- H2. CSR toward customer positively affects organizational citizenship behavior
- H3. CSR toward employee positively affects innovative behavior
- H4. CSR toward customer positively affects innovative behavior
- H5. Organizational citizenship behavior positively affects innovative behavior
- H6. Innovative behavior positively affects robustness
- H7. Innovative behavior positively affects agility
- H8. Innovative behavior positively affects integrity

4. SUMMARY DATA FINDINGS

4.1 Methods and Techniques

The following methods have been used to collect data:

Library Method: Many of the concepts and information used in this research are obtained from the study of books and articles related to the research topic, and also the websites and Persian and Latin articles available in the websites will be used. In this method, a questionnaire will be used to collect the information. The statistical population of this study is the employees of Parsian Azadi chain hotels. Data collection tools: The data collection tool in this study is the use of a standard questionnaire. Analysis of the research data consists of two parts. In order to analyze the collected data, first descriptive statistics of research demographic variables including gender, level of education and age are presented; then analytical statistics are presented. After determining the reliability and validity of the measurement tool to test the relationships and hypotheses, the correlation and regression methods using confirmatory factor analysis and in particular Structural equation modeling will be used. It should be noted that SPSS 21 and Amos statistical analysis software will be used by the researcher for the mentioned analyzes.

4.2 Validity and Reliability Of The Questionnaire

Item validity was calculated by Cronbach`s alpha coefficient.

The acceptable threshold of this analysis was 0.70 suggested by Nunnally and Bernstein (1994).

All the variables showed an acceptable reliability level ($\alpha \geq 0.70$). Cronbach`s alpha values are shown in table 4.1

Table 4.1: SPSS outcomes for Cronbach`s alpha coefficient

Variables	Cronbach`s α	result
CSR toward employee	0.759	confirmed
CSR toward customer	0.843	confirmed
ocb	0.709	confirmed
Innovative Behavior	0.805	confirmed
Integrity	0.756	confirmed
Robustness	0.843	confirmed
Agility	0.908	confirmed

Then convergent reliability was evaluated through factor analysis method which confirmed the convergent reliability of the measured items for the variables.

4.3 Methods of Data Analysis

In this study, both descriptive and deductive statistical data analysis were used for data analyzing. Perpendicular diagrams were used for assessment of replier’s information from descriptive data and descriptive data indices for the frequency distribution table and the percent. At last, structural equation modeling and particularly structural equation modeling technique was used according to the study assumptions test. For doing such analysis, SPSS 19, LISREL 8.54 were used.

4.4 Confirmatory Factor Analysis Of Research Variables

In this section data obtained using confirmatory factor analysis of each variable is presented by LISREL. Is should be noted that the obtained factor weight should be ≥ 0.3 in order to decrease the variables and taking them into account as a latent variable (Momeni and Faal Ghayoom 2017). The author, in a confirmatory factor analysis, discriminates the items and the relevant dimension, i.e. in a confirmatory factor analysis a conceptual model exists for each concept or variable of the study.

Good model fitness indicators as well as PNFI, NNFI and NFI ... the higher their value the better the model. Suggested value for these indicators is 0.9. Also, bad fitness indicators like df/χ^2 and RMSEA the less their value the better the fitness model. Allowable limit for df/χ^2 is 5 (some authors state 3). Allowable limit value for RMSEA is 1.0 (some authors state 0.08).

For replying the fitness item of the model, good and bad fit indicators should be reviewed and studied together (RMSEA, AGFI, GFI, NFI, CFI , df/χ^2 , ...). Bad fitness indicators are preferred and more effective than good indicators of fitness.

Table 4.2: Model fitness indicators

Fitness indicators	Obtained value	Allowable range	Outcome
Chi.squar/df	1.62	<3	Good fitness
RMSEA	0.55	< 0.08	Good fitness
P.Value	0.00	< 0.05	Good fitness
IFI,RFI,NNFI, NFI	91-99 %	> 90%	Good fitness

Figure 1

4.5 Findings

According to the obtained outcomes from this study, Innovative Behaviour has had a significant direct positive effect on OCB (t:2.941 st:.29), however, the effectiveness of CSRE on OCB was also confirmed in a study by Ratvanaty et.al (2020).

Analysing the obtained data also revealed that CSRE had a positive significant impact on OCB (t:11.135 st:.79) which was confirmed by Ratvanaty et.al (2020) suggesting that innovative behavior had a positive effect on OCB. The results also suggested that CSRC had no positive significant impact on OCB (t:11.92 st:.12), however, it was not in accordance with findings from Ratvanaty et.al study.

After data analyzing it was also revealed that CSRC affected OCB directly, significantly and positively, either, in a study conducted by Ratvanaty et.al these conclusions confirmed.

As it was obtained from the findings, OCB had a direct significant, positive effect on innovative behavior, but it should be reminded that Ratvanaty et.al also confirmed such results in their study (2020). Data analysis also revealed that Innovative behavior had a positive significant impact on robustness (t:12.461 st:.77).

Moreover it was suggested from findings that innovative behavior affected positively the agility (t: 11.584 st:.88), which was in accordance with those obtained from Ratvanaty et.al (2020) research.

Lastly, the present study findings improved that innovative behavior was positively effective on integrity (t: 7.932 st:.47) however, this hypothesis was also adopted by Ratvanaty et.al (2020).

5. CONCLUSION

Today, technological complications and organizational dependencies are more and higher than past and organizations are encountered with new challenges and risks rather than past. In a competitive market, to use the best strategy for surviving seems to be the vital factor, for a knowingly presence in such a changeful market. This has been appeared in many companies and organizations during Corona pandemic.

The question here is that “how some organizations can come over such events/ challenges and some fail? What enables them to win or fail such conditions? And what distinguishes these organizations from others? Certainly, organizations have plans and strategies for permanence of their business and recovering after the disasters, which will not be efficient and effective if not used within the crisis and tensions.

The key purpose of this research is to develop a model for aiding organizations to achieve their goals to continue business and their resilience against crisis and challenges. This study tried to provide tools for creating resilience view in organizations and to determine weak and strong points in point of resilience view, and to suggest recommendations for its improve and enhancement. In this regard, descriptive survey methods were used. The developed models lastly revealed that social responsibility of organization can improve organizational citizen behavior and personal and social innovative behaviors in hotel personnel and finally the organizational resilience when encountering the challenges and difficult conditions.

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